

Exploring the Role of Teachers' Associations as the Protectors of Teachers' Rights.

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Abstract

This study was undertaken to examine the role of Teachers' Associations as the protector of teachers' rights. The study is based mainly on the interviews of education experts, researchers and experienced associations' leaders. The researcher therefore intended to highlight a very important and positive role played by teachers' associations. These associations are blamed for the present faulty education system and for the lack of co-ordination among various agents of education. Associations and their active leaders at secondary school level in the province of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa were chosen as the population of the study. Interviews were conducted with union leaders for the collection of useful data. The core finding of this study suggests that most of teachers' associations are the protector of teachers' rights. They solve the problems of teachers. However, they generally support their own members during transfer, promotion and on other occasions of benefits.

Key Words:

Associations,
Problem
Solvers,
Protectors of
Rights,
Reformers

Introduction

Teachers' Associations are organizations of teacher's community and groups who are in schools as teachers are doing work for the good well of teachers and its professional progress and education system as a whole. One of the major purposes of teachers' unions and their associations is to promote teaching profession, to provide single platform to teacher community and to protect the rights of teachers. These type of unions are actually the main protectors and security guarantors of teachers' basic rights because they are to work for the deserving and basic rights of teachers, defend injustice, provide job security, work for the increase of salary, promotion and working conditions, work for betterment of teachers' community and solve their problems.

In many countries of the world, teachers' associations are considered as critically vital to educational development. They are understood as highly positive working relationship with local educational employers, government and national and international educational associations. According to Ben Levin

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(2010), all top performing countries on international level have powerful teachers' associations. They play their active and dominant role in educational policy making process, decision-taking process and educational reformation process. In this regard teachers' associations are recognized as the providers of unique resources. They are also capable of bringing innovation, modernization and reformation in the system. They solve their problems and defend the rights of their teachers through negotiation with authorities and government. Rottmann (2008) indicated that teachers' associations are the protectors of teachers' rights and the defenders of public education. They work for the professional development of teachers and make arrangement for refresher courses for teachers. These associations not only bring reforms in education system but also fight for the rights of teacher community.

Literature Review

Teachers' associations provide a common platform to all the teachers for solving their problems and for protecting their rights. Most of teachers join these teachers' associations for different purposes. Ager and Pyle (2013) led an exploration and reasoned that are essential reason for getting job in an affiliation is to find out the arrangements of the related problems. There are numerous purposes behind joining educators' relationship, among these reasons; the most popular reason is the arrangement of help in troublesome time. Affiliations offer help to their individuals at whatever point there are troubles in exchange, advancement, preparing or some other event. All associations are only can get progress when it be run professionally and by good dedicated professional peoples. As indicated by Lovenheim (2009) another critical reason for joining affiliation is to give an aggregate voice to enhancing their working conditions and to set up adaptable and satisfactory standards for advancement, pay structure and working hours. The working hours spent by the teachers in a school should be used and utilized in more original manner and style.

Kerchner and Cauffman (1993) expressed accurately that instructors' affiliations are attempting endeavors to adjust their substantial self-interests with that of the best enthusiasm of the educating calling. Bangs & Frost (2012) said that educators join relationship for building their expert limit and pioneers of the affiliations and work to guarantee limit working of the instructors. Tucker (2011) condensed that instructor associations in the United States are more composed and all the more capable. They have controlled the greater part of the parts of instruction framework even they have the specialist for the arrangement and sending of showing staff, preparing and restraining of showing staff and advancement and up-degree of educating staff. Kingdon & Teal (2008) noticed that the participation of affiliation gives educators a joined voice for taking care of their issues. They for the most part request to diminish class sizes and

increment pay rates. By doing as such unrivaled educators can be pulled in for instructing calling. Rosenberg & Silva (2012) said that joining affiliation is a beguiling piece of most educators' lives. Most instructors feel lined up with the affiliation, and would prefer not to lose the enrollment of the affiliation and the insurance gave by it. Pienaar (2006) found that the presence of relationship in schools reduces the issues of educators, so instructors focus on their showing work since they realize that affiliations' pioneers are taking care of their educating issues. Han (2012) specified that most examinations have explored that educators' affiliations assume an essential part in raising pay rates of instructors.

As indicated by the Washington Teachers' Union Report (2012) [WTU] is the main haggling delegate to discuss all issues identified with working conditions for representatives, wages and compensation, offices and hours of business. Educators are unquestionably experienced, aware and learned individuals of the group. They can without much of a stretch win the sensitivity of the general public. Through their solidarity, instructors' association can without much of a stretch accomplish their rights and can anticipate foul play through their capable devices dissents and strikes.

Sinnott (2007) said that instructors' locale is considered as a colossal power for good on the planet. In numerous parts of the world educators and their affiliations demonstrated extremely dedicated and effective in spreading instruction even in exceptionally troublesome circumstances.

As per the report of Chicago Teachers' Union (2011) 'the fundamental message of this affiliation is to win the privileges of instructors and to battle for the security of occupations and unwind working conditions'. Lukubwe (2006) said that the affiliations ought to attempt a main part in arrangement making process and in giving ways to change exercises. Their part is likewise imperative amid proficient preparing of educators. Kerchner (2001) states that affiliations can work to upgrade showing quality by advancing educator joint effort with specialists, society and different establishments. They can likewise orchestrate supplemental classes and trainings for the expert improvement of instructors. They can likewise acknowledge instructors by giving prizes and prizes. As indicated by Peterson (1999) proficient affiliations propose that instructor affiliations may not work for the self-interests of their individuals. They should work for the welfare of all instructors, understudies and establishments. Instructors' associations ought to take care of the issues of the understudies and should buckle down for the improvement of the general public alongside their self-intrigue. They should assume their fundamental part in school change on the grounds that the principle motivation behind showing calling is to make showing learning process simple. They should work for the scholastic accomplishment of understudies.

As per the OSLO report (2006) "instructor affiliations are required to use their capacities to reinforce approach making process, to lessen monetary issues

and to fathom global relations issues. Instructors associations can without much of a stretch enhance helpful undertakings for access to quality training with the coordinated effort of experts, NGOs, lawmakers and groups. They need to fortify the possibilities of their individuals for better yield, for proficient advancement and for good group relationship. They can give proficient and specialized help through workshops, courses, gatherings and productions”.

Loyo (2001) communicated that above all else affiliations rouse their own administration sides, at that point to broaden their hover of intercession, especially to the authoritative side of training framework. They work for aggregate intrigue, and inquiry out the most ideal states of their work. It is reality that educators' associations have numerous overlay purposes. Some of them are for the advancement of associations' individuals, some for the improvement of the understudies and some are for the welfare of the general public yet it is additionally certainty that the preeminent reason for existing is the aggregate enthusiasm of the individuals from that association. They need to enlarge their working circle to benefit the best working conditions, to overwhelm over instruction framework as per their own desires, and to give simplicity to their individuals, however nobody can deny the way that most educators' association accept on professional preparing, proficient advancement, consciousness of rights and obligations, arrangement of equity and equity and the improvement of training framework. As per Bill and Melinda (2010) the MET venture tries to compose an arrangement of measures that will be worthy for instructors' affiliations, executives and policymakers as solid markers of viable educating.

Educators' associations are viewed as substantial and solid pointer of gainful showing like other essential markers as approach producers, directors and instructors. These pointers are accountable for understudies' achievement as they give aptitudes, data and indicating sharpens which put inconceivable impact on understudies learning and offer quality to all parts of teaching. It infers that teachers' affiliations are useful for understudies' achievement and for the master progression of instructors. As indicated by Murillo (2002) educators' affiliations expand the homogeneity among part instructors. The aggregate activity of instructors' affiliations makes it substantially less demanding to satisfy their requests related with work dependability, work offices and employment insurance. As per Haas (2010) educators' affiliations, raise their voices for way of life issues since they have to raise their voices for essential changes in training framework. They should need to pull back ineffective parts of the framework and to present beneficial framework which underpins their way of life. It is actuality that without educators' association nobody can change the earth of instruction.

Pansiri (2013) suggested that educator relationship with the collaboration of government can without much of a stretch spotlight on change exercises and can settle every one of the issues of instructors with solidarity. They can enhance showing calling and the status of instructor group. Educators' affiliations and

government on the whole can enhance the status of instructors and the showing calling by getting general changes the field of training. Their joined endeavors can without much of a stretch settle every one of the issues existing, equity and equity among every one of the components of instruction.

It is the prime duty of these associations to work day and night for the teaching members who are unable or weak to reach their concerns to the higher managers and regulators because they cannot resolve their issues alone. These types of unions can make teachers more comfortable by standing with them when they need it for some genuine reason.

Research Methodology

Questions

1. What is/are the main purpose(s) of teachers' associations?
2. Which kind of teachers' rights are protected by teachers' associations?
3. What measures can improve the role of teachers' associations?

Research Design

This study was completed with the help of pre-designed interview questionnaire for associations' leaders. Required data were collected personally by the researcher and were properly analyzed. Findings were discussed and compared with previous researches. Conclusion was carefully drawn and some useful recommendations were given.

Population and Sampling

All the leaders of Teachers' associations along with rank holders of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan were taken as the population of the study. While one hundred well-known leaders of various teachers' associations at secondary school level were interviewed as sample of the study.

Research Instrument

A well-planned, pre-designed interview questionnaire was used for the collection of the required data. Collected data were carefully analyzed and tabulated in the form of percentage and mean score.

Data Analysis

S. No	Statements	S.A	A	UD	DA	SDA	M. score
1	Federation of teachers' can resolve the issues faced by them.	38	30	05	16	11	3.68
2	TA can make them united for getting their rights and for showing their powers.	32	44	02	18	04	3.82
3	Teachers' associations convince authorities to fulfill the needs of teachers.	27	35	10	04	24	3.37
4	Teachers' associations protect the rights of teachers.	36	37	08	11	08	3.82
5	Teachers' associations arrange professional trainings for teachers.	05	19	22	34	20	2.55
6	Teachers' associations prepare teachers to face new challenges in education.	13	19	18	35	15	2.80
7	Teachers' associations gain respect and dignity for teachers'.	15	41	12	14	18	3.21
8	Associations are the real representatives of teachers.	32	34	06	15	13	3.57
9	Unions are necessary for education system.	15	32	25	20	08	3.26
10	Associations work for the increase of salary.	41	30	06	15	08	3.81
11	Unions support their teachers in case of their service transference and promotions.	34	52	01	11	02	4.05
12	Unions can provide job security to teachers' community.	22	31	07	34	06	3.29
13	All teachers' associations are to be united for the goodness and betterment of teachers' community.	14	12	13	43	18	2.61
14	Associations may exert positive impact on teaching-learning process.	32	23	05	32	08	3.39
15	Teachers' unions' create harmony among teachers and administrators.	22	41	14	10	13	3.49

Fig: Percentage of the Agreeing Respondents

Discussion

Data indicated that amongst 100 participants, 68% agreed, 27% opted for disagreed while 5% was undecided with the statement about teachers' problems. Mean score (3.68) all support the validity and reliability of the statement. Same results were investigated by Ager and Pyle (2013). They conducted a research and investigated that teachers join association for the solution of their problems and for the provision of support in hard occasions. Kingdon (2008) also summarized that teachers' associations provide a combined voice for solving their problems. Overall more than three-quarter of the respondents, i.e 76% declared that teachers' associations keep teachers united for achieving their rights. Mean score which is 3.82, also support the statement. 62% of the respondents are agreed, 28% are disagreed with the statement that teachers' associations convince authorities to fulfill the needs of teachers. Mean score, which is 3.37, also support the statement. Teachers' associations protect the rights of teachers because a large number of 73% opted for agreed with the statement, only 19% were disagreed and 8% were not sure with the statement. Mean score (3.82) also support the statement. Chicago Teachers' Union (2011) the major purpose of teachers' associations is to win the rights of teachers. Only 24% of the teachers' association leaders reported that teachers' associations arrange professional training for teachers. A greater portion of 64% respondents are disagreed with the statement. Mean score is also very low (2.55), so the responses are accurate.

A very small number of respondents are agreed with the statement that teachers' associations prepare teachers to face new challenges in education. Half were disagreed. Mean score (2.80) also support the validity of the statement. 56%

of the association leaders suggested that teachers associations gain respect and dignity for teachers' community. 32% were disagreed while 12% were undecided. Two-third of the sample size reported that teachers' associations are the real representatives of teachers. This statement is opposed by only 28% respondents. Mean score (3.57) also highly supported the statement. 71% of the respondents declared that teachers' associations work for the increase of salary, 23% opted for disagreed while 61% were unsure about the statement. Previous researches showed that most TA worked for salaries, promotional matters, allowances or bonuses and also for making working conditions for teachers more favorable. Lovenheim (2009), teachers' associations work for attractive pay structure, promotions and better working conditions. Mostly all of the respondents, overall 86% were agreed that teachers' unions supporting its close and active union's members' in case of service transfers and promotions. Only 13% are disagreed with the statement and just one among the respondents was unsure. The mean score (4.05) which is very high, also highly supported the validity and reliability of the statement. Previous researchers also investigated that teachers' associations always promote and support their own members and ignore merit policy. More than half of the selected respondents reported that teachers' associations provide job security to teachers' community. 40% of the respondents were also against the statement. Mean score (3.29) also support the statement. According to Murillo (2002) teachers' unions made it easier to solve the teachers relevant and direct demands. 55% of the respondents opted for agreed, 40% opted for disagreed while 5% were undecided about the statement that teachers' associations exert positive impact on teaching-learning process. Mean score is above than 3 which support the statement. According to Bill and Melinda (2010) teachers' associations may provide skill, practical training, current and past knowledge with skilled teachers' and also teaching practices which may impact on educational development. Similarly Haas (2010) also found out that teachers' unions can stand against important changes in education system. Teachers' associations create harmony among teachers and administrators. This statement was approved by 63% of the respondents, only 23% opposed and 14% were unsure about the statement. Mean score was 3.49, which supported the validity of the statement.

Findings

- These types of unions and associations' may solve the problems of teachers if they work with justice and zest.
- Teachers' associations convince authorities to fulfill the needs of teachers but for it they must do in depth survey.
- They are to protect the rights of teachers and to give them awareness about it.

- Associations of teachers' gain respect and dignity for teachers.
- They are the real representatives of teachers because they are the members of the same group and so they better understand their needs.
- Associations of teachers are necessary for education system and it can develop the existing education system.
- Associations' of teachers' work for the increase of salary and other incentives so that teachers can work with much ease and comfort.
- AT should provide job security to teachers' community.
- Teachers' Unions exert positive impact on teaching-learning process.
- Associations; of teachers' create harmony among teachers and administrators.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The core findings of this study concluded that most of teachers' associations have the same motto as the protection of teachers' rights. These associations usually work to find out the problems of teachers' community and to solve them. They compel authorities to fulfill the needs and demands of teachers. Generally they make efforts to approve maximum wages, high scales and more allowances and attractive working conditions for teachers. Most of teachers' associations try to push the members of their own associations forward for promotion, up-gradation and occupying the key posts. These teachers' associations display their power and unity by huge meetings, strikes and protests for achieving their rights. The job of all such unity and associations are to give good well and fame to their concerned institutes to make them more great and workable. On the basis of conclusion, some possible recommendations were suggested to improve the role of teachers' associations. These recommendations are:

1. Teachers' associations may work for the welfare of students, teachers, and education system and for the welfare of community.
2. Teachers' associations may solve their problems by negotiations with authorities on legal ways and not by strikes and protests.
3. Teachers' associations may not give favor to their own members, but may work on the basis of merit.
4. TU leaders should provide themselves as the real representatives of the teacher's community.
5. Teachers' associations may improve teaching-learning process by arranging workshops, seminars and refresher courses.
6. Teachers' associations may prepare students and teachers to face new challenges which are arising in education very rapidly.
7. Teachers' associations may gain dignity and respect for teachers by bringing reforms and innovations in education system.

8. Teachers' associations may prove their practical contribution and positive impacts on education system.
9. All teachers' associations may bond in one single federation to show their single unity and power. Collectively they will get their rights very easily.
10. Teachers' associations may create harmony among teachers, administrators and authorities. They may also create harmony among all the agents of education system.

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